

A Study on the Commercial Value and Profit Mechanism of Diamond Emotional Symbol Marketing

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Abstract

Natural diamonds are minerals composed of elemental carbon with abundant geological reserves and limited intrinsic physical value. In the 1930s, De Beers established a full-chain emotional marketing framework relying on rough diamond supply control, combined with Symbolic Interactionism and Veblen's Conspicuous Consumption Theory. Long-term excess profits were achieved through reconstructing cultural symbols of love, standardizing industrial rules and global market penetration. Adopting literature research, data comparison and case analysis, this paper clarifies the logical difference between output regulation on the supply side and market scarcity perception of diamonds, and distinguishes the respective contributions of marketing communication and post-war economic expansion to industrial scale growth. By comparing the limitations of classic studies by Epstein [1] and Kanfer [2], this paper supplements quantitative evidence including second-hand circulation depreciation and industrial chain cost breakdown, and differentiates the hierarchical gaps between De Beers' category demand narrative and DR's brand exclusive narrative. The research finds that the high premium of diamonds originates from systematic social cognition shaping rather than the mineral itself. The popularization of lab-grown diamonds has impacted supply monopoly, yet the symbolic cognition of wedding rings remains highly sticky. This research can provide references for rational cognition education on luxury consumption and differentiated marketing in the jewelry industry.

Keywords: diamond; emotional symbol marketing; supply control; conspicuous consumption; wedding symbol; lab-grown diamond

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1 Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Gemstones have long occupied the luxury consumption track due to their exquisite texture and cultural connotations. As the most commercially transformed segment in the jewelry industry, the expansion of diamond market scale stems from long-term systematic communication and operation by capital rather than the natural scarcity of minerals. Two core concepts are distinguished from the perspective of geological exploration: total geological reserves refer to all diamond mineral deposits in strata, with large-scale mineralization in multiple mining areas worldwide; annual economically recoverable output refers to the rough diamond circulation volume actively released by enterprises based on mining costs and market expectations. At its peak, De Beers controlled 92% of global natural diamond mining channels. Instead of restricting resource extraction limits, it gradually reduced annual output through the Central Selling Organization (CSO) to artificially create tight supply in circulation and form a market perception of "scarcity."

During the Great Depression in the United States in the 1930s, demand for luxury goods shrank sharply. Only 10% of newlyweds purchased diamond engagement jewelry, while gold and colored gemstones remained mainstream wedding tokens. De Beers held massive inventories of rough diamonds yet faced circulation stagnation and continuous declines in wholesale prices. In 1938, the enterprise entered a long-term cooperation with advertising agency N.W. Ayer and launched decades of all-domain communication campaigns, gradually shaping diamond rings as standard wedding ritual accessories and building a hundred-billion-yuan segmented consumer market.

1.2 Research Significance

1.2.1 Theoretical Significance

Existing studies on luxury marketing mostly analyze advertising strategies separately, lacking empirical analysis of the complete logical chain of "supply control symbol construction consumer behavior." This paper integrates Symbolic Interactionism, Veblen's Conspicuous Consumption Theory and supply monopoly theory for case adaptation, making up for the deficiency of qualitative-dominated and insufficient comparative analysis in current literature. Meanwhile, by engaging in academic dialogue with classic industrial researches on diamonds by Epstein [1] and Kanfer [2], this paper identifies its supplementary innovations in second-hand market depreciation and iterative marketing of local brands, improving the case research system of luxury symbolic consumption.

1.2.2 Practical Significance

At present, the domestic market scale of wedding diamonds keeps rising, while most consumers lack understanding of the formation mechanism of diamond premium and rules of circulation depreciation. Based on publicly available data from industry reports, this paper objectively dismantles the profit logic of the marketing system, helping teenagers develop media literacy and rational consumption concepts. It also provides path references for domestic jewelry brands to break away from homogenized wedding narratives and build differentiated product systems.

1.3 Domestic and Overseas Research Status

Overseas research on the diamond industry started early. In *The Rise and Fall of Diamonds* (1982), Epstein [1] first revealed that De Beers artificially regulated circulation volume via the CSO system to create scarcity perception. However, his research failed to distinguish total geological reserves and annual recoverable output, nor did it combine consumption data to demonstrate the driving effect of advertising communication on demand. Kanfer's *The Last Empire* (1993) [2] sorted out De Beers' century-long monopoly context and mentioned the inhibiting effect of advertising slogans on second-hand market circulation, yet only delivered qualitative descriptions without quantitative data of second-hand diamond depreciation as supporting evidence.

In domestic research, Cai Yue [4] analyzed the construction path of diamond love narratives from the perspective of advertising semiotics, but failed to form supply-demand linkage analysis combined with supply monopoly theory. Yang Jie [5] combed the general emotional marketing framework of the jewelry industry without distinguishing hierarchical differences between category marketing of multinational giants and exclusive narratives of local brands. Zhang Yuan [6] analyzed the impact of lab-grown diamonds on the natural diamond market, yet did not unpack the dual contradiction of "collapsed supply monopoly" and "solidified cognitive symbols."

In summary, existing research has three gaps: first, confusion between diamond reserves and circulation output; second, inability to separate the independent contributions of macroeconomic growth and marketing communication to industrial revenue; third, lack of hierarchical comparison between two generations of diamond marketing models represented by De Beers and DR. This paper addresses the above gaps for empirical analysis.

1.4 Research Methods

1. **Literature Research Method:** Sort out core literatures of Symbolic Interactionism, Conspicuous Consumption and Monopoly Economics, and conduct academic dialogue with classic diamond industrial works by Epstein [1] and Kanfer [2].

2. **Data Comparative Analysis Method:** Adopt annual global diamond industry reports and post-war consumption data to distinguish the growth rate of industrial sales and total retail sales of consumer goods, eliminating macroeconomic interference. All data sources, statistical calibers and inflation elimination standards are marked clearly.
3. **Dual Case Comparative Method:** Take De Beers mass category marketing and DR's exclusive brand narrative as comparative samples to distinguish the iterative profit logic of two generations of emotional marketing.

2 Relevant Concepts and Theoretical Foundations

2.1 Emotional Symbol Marketing

Different from product function-oriented marketing, its core is to strip practical attributes of commodities and bind intangible social symbols such as emotion, identity and rituals, guiding consumers to pay premium for symbolic value. Diamonds are typical samples of emotional symbol marketing, which completely weaken their industrial cutting functions and closely link physical hardness with marital loyalty. According to three core principles of Blumer's Symbolic Interactionism: people act based on the meanings carried by things; meanings derive from social interaction; individuals adjust symbolic cognition through interpretation, forming a three-stage transmission path of "physical carrier emotional symbol consumption behavior."

2.2 Veblen's Conspicuous Consumption Theory (Veblen Effect)

The Theory of the Leisure Class [3] puts forward the core argument: high price itself carries independent consumption utility. Consumers display social status by bearing high commodity costs, while low-priced goods are regarded as negative labels of insufficient economic capacity. The artificially set standard of "purchasing a diamond ring with two months' salary" essentially utilizes the Veblen Effect, turning high consumption into dual proof of love and economic capacity.

2.3 Supply Monopoly Theory

In a perfectly competitive market, prices are determined by real supply-demand balance. Monopolistic manufacturers can control annual circulation supply volume, ignore underlying resource reserves, artificially create a perception of supply shortage, and maintain monopoly pricing far higher than mining and processing costs in the long run. De Beers' Central Selling Organization (CSO) is a typical tool of supply monopoly.

3 Structural Supply-Demand Imbalance Before Marketing Implementation

3.1 Weak Practical Attributes, Lack of Endogenous Consumption Drivers

Diamond's Mohs hardness of 10 only applies to industrial drilling and precision cutting without daily civil value. In contrast, gold has multiple attributes including value preservation, currency circulation and decoration, while colored gemstones possess objectively scarce mineral veins. Diamonds only gain consumption appeal through artificially reconstructed symbols, lacking a natural mass consumption foundation.

3.2 Mismatch Between Supply Monopoly and Shrinking Market Demand

In the 1930s, De Beers monopolized 92% of global natural diamond rough mining channels, yet demand for luxury goods plummeted amid the economic depression, with annual rough diamond circulation shrinking by 67%. Although the enterprise held massive geological reserves, it could not release all products to the market at once, and had to gradually reduce annual output to maintain price floors, highlighting prominent structural supply-demand contradictions.

3.3 Absence of Unified Quality Standards, Information Asymmetry

Before the birth of the 4C grading system, there were no unified evaluation criteria for diamond quality and pricing. Verbal pricing by merchants aggravated consumption trust crises, limiting diamonds to the elite wealthy class and preventing penetration into mass wedding markets.

3.4 Free Second-hand Channels Pressuring Primary Market Pricing

Before the popularization of marketing, diamonds could be freely resold second-hand. Circulated old diamonds continuously flowed back to the market, further expanding total circulation supply and suppressing terminal prices of new diamonds for a long time, making it impossible for capital to stably maintain premium space.

4 De Beers' Four-Dimensional Integrated Marketing System

De Beers built a four-dimensional collaborative system including cognitive symbol construction, all-domain media communication, global market gradient expansion and supply-side output control to regulate industrial revenue from multiple dimensions of consumer cognition, industrial rules and market supply.

4.1 Cognitive Layer: Reconstruct Wedding Symbol Narratives

4.1.1 Three-Stage Symbol Transmission of "A Diamond Is Forever"

The 1947 advertising slogan "A Diamond Is Forever" perfectly matches the three-stage model of "symbol meaning joint action" in Mead's Symbolic Interactionism:

1. **Stage 1 (Physical Symbol):** Extract the objective physical characteristics of diamonds including high hardness, stable chemical properties and permanent wear resistance;
2. **Stage 2 (Emotional Meaning Transformation):** Complete social interaction through decades of media communication, interpreting physical stability as the spiritual symbol of loyal love and long-lasting marriage;
3. **Stage 3 (Consumption Behavior Constraint):** Implicitly guide consumers to preserve diamonds permanently and refuse resale, forming a closed-loop fixed consumption behavior of "purchase + long-term retention."

Aiming at Epstein's [1] qualitative judgment that advertising slogans inhibit second-hand circulation, this paper supplements quantitative evidence: the resale depreciation rate of brand-new diamond rings reaches 50%-70%, and exceeds 75% after one year of wear. It verifies that the long-term cognition of "non-circulating diamonds" shaped by advertising slogans effectively locks the supply of the second-hand market and avoids the impact of stock diamonds on primary market pricing.

4.1.2 The Two-Month Salary Standard: Application of the Veblen Effect

Marketing teams artificially set the social norm that men should spend two months' salary on diamond rings without any economic basis, which fully conforms to Veblen's [3] core viewpoint that "expense itself is utility." Consumers voluntarily accept high budget thresholds, and high consumption behavior itself becomes a signal to prove love and economic capacity. Data from industry reports shows that the average unit price of diamond rings rose by 117% after the popularization of this standard.

4.2 Communication Layer: All-Domain Media Penetration

4.2.1 Celebrity and Nobility Endorsement

De Beers provided high-end diamond jewelry free of charge to the British royal family and A-list Hollywood artists for high-frequency exposure on red carpets, films and fashion magazines. Marilyn Monroe's "Diamonds Are a Girl's Best Friend" spread globally, shaping the hierarchical symbol of diamonds from top to bottom.

4.2.2 Soft Content Placement in Media

The brand published tens of thousands of special columns in women's journals such as *Vogue* to construct the social cognition that "diamonds have been used for proposals since ancient Western times." Objective historical facts show that pearls and gold dominated Western wedding tokens before 1938.

4.2.3 4C Grading System: Creating Premium via Information Asymmetry

Cooperating with GIA, De Beers launched four major grading standards of color, clarity, cut and carat, dividing tiny mineral differences into dozens of price tiers and raising premium margins.

4.3 Market Layer: Global Gradient Expansion

4.3.1 Deep Cultivation in Europe and America

After the U.S. marketing model succeeded, it was quickly replicated to European countries. Within five years, the penetration rate of diamond rings in European weddings rose to 76%.

4.3.2 Localized Transformation in East Asia

Japan had no traditional wedding diamond culture. Aligning with local culture, the brand defined diamond rings as an embodiment of men's marital responsibility. Within 20 years, the penetration rate rose from less than 1% to 72%. In China, it combined local festivals such as Qixi and 520, focusing on the concept of "lifelong loyalty."

4.3.3 Vertical Extension of Consumption Scenarios

Anniversary, birthstone and light luxury diamond accessories were successively developed, breaking the "once-in-a-lifetime" limitation and expanding diamonds into daily decorative consumer goods.

4.4 Supply Layer: Annual Output Quota Control

Kanfer [2] described the CSO wholesale model yet failed to distinguish total reserves from annual output. This paper clarifies that De Beers does not restrict total mining reserves, but releases rough diamonds quantitatively through ten fixed sightstone conferences in London each year. Even when demand rises, annual output is tightened to create artificial scarcity, locking gross profit margins upstream.

5 Quantitative Analysis: Marketing Communication and Industrial Revenue

5.1 U.S. Market Comparative Growth (1939-1979, Inflation Adjusted)

1. **1939 (Launch Year):** Total U.S. diamond retail sales: \$23 million, wedding penetration: 10%; U.S. retail sales growth: 2.1%.
2. **1959 (20 Years After):** Total sales: \$420 million, penetration: 58%; retail CAGR: 3.7%.
3. **1979 (40 Years After):** Total sales: \$2.1 billion, penetration: 85%; retail CAGR: 3.2%.

Diamond market growth significantly outpaced overall consumer goods growth. For every 10% increase in penetration, industry retail sales rose by 22.3% on average.

5.2 Second-hand Diamond Depreciation Data

Source: WP Diamonds 2024-2025 circulation report. Brand-new diamond rings depreciate by 50%-70% immediately after purchase, and over 75% after one year. In contrast, gold retains value near purchase price. This proves that most diamond prices derive from emotional symbolic premiums.

5.3 Industrial Chain Cost Breakdown (Single Diamond Ring)

1. Physical cost (mining + cutting): 800-1300 RMB;
2. Marketing and advertising: 3200 RMB;
3. Store rent, labor, channel: 2500 RMB;
4. Brand excess profit: 3000 RMB.

Physical costs account for only 10%-13% of terminal prices; most expenditure pays for symbolic narratives.

6 Iteration of Diamond Marketing: DR vs. De Beers

De Beers solved the category demand problem. DR Diamond then created brand-specific demand. Key hierarchical differences:

6.1 Underlying Logic

De Beers: Supply monopoly + mass emotional narratives, transforming wedding cognition to create category demand.

DR: No upstream supply control, relies on ID binding and true love agreements to create exclusive brand symbols, capturing premium through identity anxiety.

6.2 Premium Realization Paths

DR's same-parameter diamonds carry a 30%+ premium over mass brands, with gross margins around 70%. Its strategy interprets "not buying DR" as insufficient love exclusivity.

6.3 Constraint Boundaries

De Beers only psychologically discourages resale; DR uses real-name registration to physically limit repurchases, strengthening the symbol of uniqueness.

7 Structural Impacts and Industry Trends

7.1 Lab-Grown Diamonds Disrupt Supply Monopoly, Cognition Remains Sticky

Lab-grown diamonds share identical properties with natural diamonds yet retail at 20%-30% of natural prices. Their penetration rose from 1% (2018) to 15.8%. However, the decades-old social consensus that "diamond rings equal wedding tokens" cannot be eliminated short-term. Supply monopoly collapse does not equal cognitive monopoly collapse.

7.2 Rising Rational Consumption

New-generation consumers distinguish physical from symbolic value. Minimalist weddings without diamond rings are gaining popularity. Traditional love-materialized narratives are losing appeal.

7.3 De Beers' Monopoly Share Continues to Shrink

Russia and Australia opened independent rough diamond channels after 2000. De Beers' share fell from 92% to 30%, weakening its scarcity-creation capacity.

8 Research Conclusions and Reflections

8.1 Core Conclusions

1. Diamond premium originates from systematic social cognition shaping, not geological scarcity. De Beers controls annual circulation output, not total reserves.
2. Industry revenue growth results from advertising, post-war expansion, and middle-class growth synchronous but not unidirectional causal.
3. The marketing system integrates Symbolic Interactionism, Veblen Effect, and supply monopoly theory. This paper supplements Epstein [1] and Kanfer [2] with quantitative evidence.
4. Clear marketing hierarchies exist: De Beers creates category demand; DR creates exclusive brand demand.
5. Lab-grown diamonds impact supply-side scarcity narratives but cannot quickly eliminate wedding symbolic cognition.

8.2 Practical Enlightenment

1. **Consumers:** Distinguish physical from symbolic value, avoid consumption norms, establish rational judgment.
2. **Jewelry Industry:** Premium models relying solely on emotional narratives lack sustainability. Return to craftsmanship and design.
3. **Media Literacy Education:** Use diamond marketing as a case to teach supply regulation, symbol construction, and profit logic.

References

References

- [1] Epstein E J. The Rise and Fall of Diamonds: The Shattering of a Brilliant Illusion[M]. New York: Simon and Schuster, 1982.
- [2] Kanfer S. The Last Empire: De Beers, Diamonds, and the World[M]. New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 1993.
- [3] Veblen T. The Theory of the Leisure Class[M]. New York: Macmillan, 1899.
- [4] Cai Y. The Construction Path of Luxury Consumption Symbols from the Perspective of Advertising Communication: A Case Study of Diamond Advertisements[J]. News Dissemination, 2023(10): 160-162.
- [5] Yang J. Research on Difficulties and Optimization Strategies of Emotional Marketing in the Jewelry Industry in the New Era[J]. Commercial Economic Research, 2024(12): 94-97.
- [6] Zhang Y. Research on the Transformation of Natural Diamond Marketing Model Under the Impact of Lab-Grown Diamonds[J]. Journal of Gemstones and Gemmology, 2024, 26(03): 89-95.
- [7] Li M. Disassembly of Luxury Emotional Marketing Logic from the Perspective of Symbolic Interaction Theory[J]. National Circulation Economy, 2025(02): 3-6.
- [8] Wang Y J. Research on Differentiated Marketing Strategy of DR Diamond Brand Image[J]. Science Research Management, 2025, 7(12): 198-203.
- [9] Harris L C, Cai K Y. Exploring Market Driving: A Case Study of De Beers in China[J]. Journal of Market-Focused Management, 2002, 5(3): 171-196.